

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

D5.2. GEPVISION on-line tool

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Grant Agreement n°: 101006416

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

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Version history

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	30/05/2022	Draft	Noemi Biancone, Fernando Ferri, Patrizia Grifoni, Alessia Marino
1.0	26/07/2022	Final	Noemi Biancone, Fernando Ferri, Patrizia Grifoni
1.1	27/07/2022	Final	Review by Cira Mendoza

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP5
Task	T5.2
Deliverable	D5.2 GEPVISION on-line tool
Due Date	31/07/2022
Submission Date	31/07/2022
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	CNR
Version	1.1
Status	Final
Author (s)	Noemi Biancone, Fernando Ferri, Patrizia Grifoni, Alessia Marino
Reviewers	Project Coordinator

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CE	Consulta Europa
FRCT	Fundo Regional para a Cienciac e Tecnologia
GOBCAN	Gobierno de Canarias
JSI	Institut Jozef Stefan
UB	Universitatea din Bucuresti
UJK	Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach
ULPGC	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
UVSK SAV	Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej AKADEMIE VIED

1. Introduction

This deliverable is related to the activities and results produced within the task “T5.2- GEPVISION”, which are about the configuration of the tool for continuous GEPs monitoring named GEPVISION.

GEPVISION is an on-line tool aiming to facilitate data collection from the GEPs, its monitoring and visualisation of indicators, providing evidence of changes in the different organisations, helping the organisations to self-evaluate progresses within their GEPs.

This tool has been configured following the GEPs defined within “WP4-G EPS Development and implementation”, the strategies and indicators framework defined with the task “T5.1-Development of GEPs monitoring and evaluation system” and described in the deliverable “D5.1-Guidelines on monitoring and evaluation” for monitoring Gender Equality Plans.

2. Preliminary concepts

GEPVISION, following the same logic of the M&E System defined in the deliverable D5.1, is based on the five intervention areas identified in the Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans [\[1\]](#):

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision making
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content
5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

The monitoring process for each GEP in the different areas is carried out considering the outputs and outcomes of GEPs. In particular, the outputs will be monitored using the indicators (qualitative and quantitative) for the GEPs action implementation, i.e., they provide a picture of the GEP implementation process measuring the progress at the level of specific actions. The outcomes will be monitored using the indicators (qualitative and quantitative) measuring the progress at the overall impact level within the organisation where the GEP is implemented (measuring changes produced).

Therefore, the monitoring process requires: 1) customising the GEPs, identifying targets and periodicity for each indicator, 2) collecting data related to the outcomes from the pilot organisations submitted periodically, 3) collecting data on the actions carried out within the implemented GEPs related to the outputs), 4) analysis of all data collected.

As the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan is customised for each institution, the GEPVISION system has been designed to enable the customisation of the different indicators and their evolution according to the potential evolution of GEPs and, to facilitate data collection and visualisation.

3. GEPVISION

This section describes the functionalities designed and planned within the GEPVISION tool. The functionalities of GEPVISION are the following: 1) Manage GEP, 2) Manage indicators, 3) Fill in GEPs, 4) Visualise data collected, also using graphs and smartcards.

Each organisation implementing its GEP can periodically update data about the GEP implementation in terms of output and outcomes in GEPVISION, facilitating activities of self-evaluation and monitoring.

The GEPVISION tool is available at:

<https://www.athena-gepvision.eu/>

The configured functionalities have been used by CNR and will be used by the ATHENA organisations implementing the GEPs according to their differences, enabling customised data collection and visualisation.

The following sub-sections will describe the four types of functionalities and their use.

3.1 Manage GEP

GEPVISION will enable each organisation that is implementing a GEP to manage it. i.e.:

- to edit the description of the organisation (see point 1 in Figure 1)
- to define and modify the set of output and outcome indicators and thresholds related to the GEP (see point 2 of Figure 1)

- to appoint people of the organisation who are enabled to manage the GEP. Only people established by the organisation can interact with and manage data. Each organisation can nominate a “manager” or a “supervisor” (points 4 and 5 in Figure 1). A manager can fill in GEPs and be in charge of one GEP only. A supervisor is a GEP administrator. She or he appoints the manager roles, can edit the description of the organisation and can add indicators, parameters and thresholds to her or his GEPs.

Each organisation decides if data related to the GEP will be visualised only by authorised people or by all users (point 6 in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Manage GEP

Aiming to add or modify the description of the organisation, the supervisor can select "Edit description", adding or changing the text of the description.

Based on the GEP defined by the organisation and the common template (see Table 1) used for defining outputs and outcomes indicators, the supervisor can add the indicators

Table 1. Framework for customising GEPs

Area in the EU GEP Guidance	Objectives/Goals/Challenges	Action within the GEP in Athena	State of the action	Description of the action	Indicators	Thresholds	Direct target	Person in Charge, her role within the Organisation	Time frame	Sources	Outcomes/ results	Remarks/ Obstacle
Work-life balance and organisational culture	Objective 1.1.: Identify the objective(s)/ goals – your “vision of change” in the area. This should be the basis for choosing appropriate gender indicators against which to track progress.	Action 1.1.1. Define activity (ies) relating to the specific objective.		Describe in short the action: what kind of work/tasks you are planning to do within the activity.								
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Objective 2.1.	Action 2.1.1.										
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Objective 3.1.	Action 2.1.2.										
		Action 3.1.1.										
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Objective 4.1.	Action 3.1.2.										
		Action 4.1.1.										
Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Objective 5.1.	Action 5.1.1.										

The supervisor clicks on “Add output indicator” or on “Add outcome indicator” for adding a new indicator to monitor the GEP activities then they select one of the five "Intervention areas" related to the indicator as defined in the guidance [1].

Figure 2. Selection of the intervention areas

She or he fills in the Indicator name and selects the option Qualitative or Quantitative (according to the type of indicator) as in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Definition of an indicator filling in the name and the type

Clicking on “Add supervisor” or on “Add manager” (Figure1) each organisation can add them (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Adding a Manager/Supervisor, it is possible to add a manager or a supervisor of the GEP for each organisation

3.2 Manage indicators

Managing the GEP enables the addition of new indicators (Figure 2 and Figure 3). Each indicator needs to be customised with the specific GEP.

Let us consider as an example the indicator “Number of children at the workplace nursery”; we need to specify some parameters (Figure 5). For example, we need to establish when we go to measure the value for the indicator. We decided to monitor it by year; therefore, we add the variable Year and the supervisor can also add the thresholds that enables to evaluate as Not Satisfactory, Satisfactory or Very satisfactory the values observed for the indicator during the years (Figure 6).

Figure 5. configuration of parameters for the indicators

Figure 6. Configuration of thresholds

3.3 Fill in GEPs

Each organisation has to collect data for periodic monitoring of the GEP, and elaborating new strategies for strengthen the actions related to Gender Equality. Once defined and managed the Indicators, managers of the GEPs can fill in the data collected.

GEPVISION was implemented to simplify data collection. In particular, each manager can download a Pdf writable file from GEPVISION containing the GEP schema of the organisation.

Indeed, each manager can click on “Download editable PDF file” (Figure 7). The file can be filled in at different times and without the need to be on-line (see the example in Figure 8). Then the file can be uploaded (Figure 9).

Figure 7. Download the editable PDF file

Athena

Gender Balance for Innovation

GEP di JSI

Number of children at the workplace nursery

Year	Value
2022	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text" value="10"/>
2023	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>
2024	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>

Note:

Action:

Cooperation with workplace nursery

Figure 8. Fill GEP data in the editable PDF file

Home Show users GEP Organization survey

DOWNLOAD EDITABLE PDF FILE

UPLOAD EDITABLE PDF FILE

Number of children at the workplace nursery

● Year

SHOW VALUES

Year	Value
2022	10
2023	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>
2024	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>

Enter a note

Cooperation with workplace nursery

Figure 9. Data saved from the uploaded pdf file

3.4 To visualise data collected

GEPVISION enables visualising data collected for each GEP using Smart cards, Vertical Bar Chart, Horizontal Bar Chart, Stacked Bar Chart, and Line Chart (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Data visualisation by Smart card and graphs

4. Conclusion

The GEPVISION tool is available on-line at:

<https://www.athena-gepvision.eu/login>

Each partner implementing a GEP indicates at least one supervisor and one manager. They, jointly with CNR, are habilitated to manage their GEP, indicators and to fill in data collected. A video related to GEPVISION functioning is available at:

<https://youtu.be/do6AGoTONzE>

Webinars will be done within the partners that are implementing the GEPs. It is compulsory that each organisation will collect data for monitoring activities

starting from Month 22, 34 and 46, aiming to produce the “D5.3 - GEP implementation monitoring reports - v1”, “D5.4 - GEP implementation monitoring reports – vfinal”, and “Impact report”.

5. Bibliography

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